

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF THE TEMPERATURE OF ELECTRIC MOTOR WINDINGS BASED ON THE TOTAL INSTANTANEOUS POWER VALUE MEASURED 15 MS AFTER START-UP

Kobozev A.,

Candidate of Technical Sciences

Smilyanskiy I.

Candidate of Technical Sciences

ABSTRACT

It is proposed to use the windings themselves as a thermistor to determine the temperature of electric motor windings at each next start. Such a useful function of windings at frequent starts (intermittent mode) is realized by analyzing the character of change in the total instantaneous power within 20 ms after the moment of start. It is shown that the winding temperature is determined by only one discrete instantaneous power value corresponding to a time of 15 ms after the motor start. A simple algorithm of operation of the microprocessor device is given when the windings of electric motors realize the function of thermistor.

Keywords: total instantaneous power, winding temperature, time constant.

Currently, leading companies for the protection of electric motors (EMs) operating in intermittent mode offer protective relays that, during overload currents, are triggered not by exceeding a given value of the Joule integral (I^2t), but by exceeding the current value [1]. Since the lifetime of the overload current with such dynamic protection is limited to only a few seconds, this makes it possible to restart the motor much faster. Note that when triggered by an integral setpoint, the restart time is often only possible via ($2 \div 4$) minutes. It is quite obvious that the productivity of industrial complexes when using dynamic protection increases significantly.

But the refusal to use the Joule integral makes it necessary to control the temperature mode of the EM with the help of thermistors. This means that to implement dynamic protection of electric motors, thermistors must be installed in their windings. Therefore, in order to be able to realize dynamic protection also for EM without thermistors in their windings, the task of using EM windings themselves as thermistors seems to be very attractive.

The purpose of this article is to substantiate the possibility of using EM windings as thermistors by analyzing the change in the character of EM power in the transient mode. It will be shown that the temperature of the windings is determined, essentially, by just one instantaneous power value corresponding to the time instant of 15 ms after the start of the electric motor.

It is not possible to determine the change in winding temperature by the decrease in current caused by an increase in their active resistance when heated. So the magnitude of the change in current, even when the windings are heated by 100, will be commensurate with the value of the current measurement error. It seems more productive to determine the change in resistance by monitoring the generalized time constant (τ) of the EM windings when they are heated. To do this, it is necessary to select for analysis a parameter of the start-up process, the value of which can be used to reliably determine the value of τ . The specified parameter

must meet certain requirements. One of these requirements is due to the fact that as the electric motor “accelerates”, the value of the time constant of its windings τ will change. Therefore, the determination of the reduced time constant of the windings must be done very quickly, within first period of change in the starting current. This means that the analysis of the nature of the change in the parameter for, chosen to determine the value of τ , should be carried out in a transient mode. The second requirement for the above parameter is that the nature of its change depends only on the value of the time constant.

It is known that the character of phase current change in transient mode depends both on the value of time constant τ , and on the moment of inrush current occurrence. This also applies to the character of power change in one EMs phase. The dependence of the character of the above parameters on the moment of current occurrence is caused by the fact that their values in steady-state mode are not constant but change with time. Therefore, it is necessary to have such a parameter of the start-up process of an electric motor, the value of which is a constant value in the steady-state mode. In this case, the nature of the change in this parameter in the transient mode will depend solely on the time constant τ . One of these parameters is the total active power of all three phases, which in a symmetrical steady state is a constant value independent of time.

In our article [2], in which the issue of blocking inrush currents as undesirable disturbances in the construction of protection against short-circuit currents was considered, the dependence of the change of the total instantaneous power $P(t)$ in the transient period of the start-up time of the EM was obtained, which has the following form:

$$P(t) = 3UI \left[\cos\varphi - \cos(\omega t + \varphi) e^{-t/\tau} \right], \quad (1)$$

where: U and I are, respectively, the effective values of phase voltage and current. Note that the phase angle φ is determined through $\tau \cdot \text{tg}(\varphi) = \omega\tau$.

Fig.1 Dependency $P=f(t)$ at different values τ

Fig.1 shows the dependences $P(t)$ for the following four values of time constant τ - 5 ms, 10 ms, 15 ms and 20 ms. The character of change of the presented dependences $P(t)$ has the form of damped oscillations from the value P_{\max} to the value P_{\min} . At that, as it can be seen from the given graphs, with the change of the value τ the maximum power value P_{\max} changes very insignificantly. Whereas the value of P_{\min} changes very significantly with the change of the value of τ . This means that the minimum value of the instantaneous starting power P_{\min} allows to determine the value time constant τ and, accordingly, the winding temperature. It should be noted that at all values of the value τ the value of the instantaneous power

reaches its minimum value P_{\min} always 15 ms after the moment of the starting time of the EM. It follows that by controlling the value of the total instantaneous power 15 ms after the start - P_{15} , it is possible to control the thermal operation mode of the EM.

In order to estimate the significance of the parameter P_{15} for determining the winding temperature change within the permissible limits, Fig. 2 shows the dependence of the time constant τ from the relative value of the total instantaneous power, corresponding to 15 ms after the start - P_{15} , to the average value of the total power during the first period (20 ms) of the starting current change P_{1T} -

$$P'_{15} = P_{15} / P_{1T} \cdot$$

Fig.2 Dependence of value τ on value P'_{15}

If, for example, the initial value of the time constant is equal to $\tau=15\text{ms}$ ($\cos \varphi \approx 0,2$), then heating the copper windings by 150 will decrease the value of the time constant to $\tau=9,4\text{ms}$ ($\cos \varphi \approx 0,35$). This change in the time constant τ , corresponds to a change in the power value P'_{15} from (-0.48) to (+0.3). It means that the value of the total instantaneous power in 15 ms after start-up P'_{15} is indeed a significant parameter for estimating the temperature of the windings of the electric motor at each next start-up.

Thus, it can be stated, that by analyzing the total instantaneous power 15 ms after start-up, the EM windings can perform the function of a thermistor. It should

be noted the following advantage of using windings as thermistors in comparison with the use of thermistors mounted in the stator winding of the electric motor. Since in motors with a power of more than 15 kW, it is not the stator windings that are critical for rapid heating, but the rotor windings, and thermal relays, using thermistors built into the stator windings, may not have time to respond to the rapid heating of the rotor winding in the mode of frequent starts of the motor. In the case of using EM windings as thermistors, the weighted average temperature value of both the stator and rotor windings is determined.

Fig.3 Algorithm for the implementation of the thermistor function by ED windings

The operating algorithm of the microprocessor device for implementing the thermistor function by the ED windings is shown in Fig. 3. The modules presented in Fig. 3 do not physically exist; they denote a certain mathematical operation.

In module 1, an array of instantaneous power values $P(t)$ is recorded for the first period of change in the starting current. In the same module, the value of instantaneous power is recorded at a time of 15 ms after the start moment - value P_{15} and the average power value for the first period of change in the starting current is determined - value P_{17} .

In module 2, determine the relative value P'_{15} , equal to $P'_{15} = P_{15}/P_{17}$.

In module 3, using the dependence $\tau = f(P'_{15})$, the current value of the time constant τ_j of the EM windings is determined. The dependence $\tau = f(P'_{15})$ can be presented in tabular form or an approximated dependence can be found.

In module 4, the ratio of the initial value τ_1 (at the first start) to the current value of the time constant $\tau_j - K_\tau = \tau_1/\tau_j$ is determined.

In module 5, the value of the temperature rise of the windings is determined at each regular start of the electric motor. Due to the fact that aluminum windings are used in electric motors for mass use (in refrigerators, vacuum cleaners, etc.) to obtain an economic effect, the expression for temperature is given for copper windings $\theta_j = (K_\tau - 1)/0,004C^0$.

Then, based on a comparison of the obtained temperature rise value with the permissible value, a conclusion is made about the possibility of continuing or interrupting the next start-up process.

Resume. *The possibility of determining the winding temperature at each next start of the ED by using the ED windings in the function of thermistors is substantiated. Such function of windings is realized at the expense of analysis of character of change of total power in time in the first period of change of starting current. It is shown that at each start-up of an electric motor the temperature of its windings is reliably enough determined by only one instantaneous power value corresponding to the moment of time 15 ms from the moment of start-up of the electric motor. A simple algorithm of the microprocessor device operation is given when realizing the thermistor function by the ED windings.*

Giving the thermistor function to the ED windings allows to apply dynamic (without integral set point) protection of such EDs, in the windings of which thermistors are not installed.

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